

Mineralogical and geochemical characteristics of the Sedemte Prestola potassic alkaline pluton

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Abstract. The Sedemte Prestola pluton is an intermediate to acid plutonic body of Variscan age (308.7 ± 9.1 Ma). Despite its small size, several petrographic varieties are present: syenites, quartzsyenites and granites. It is composed of potassium feldspar, quartz, sodic-calcic amphibole; biotite, when present, is often rimmed by amphibole or strongly altered; zircon, titanite, apatite and ilmenite are the accessory phases. The rocks display pronounced potassic character with up to 10.4 wt% K_2O , peralkaline tendency, and significant trace element enrichment for REE, Zr, Th, U, and Ba. The rocks also show enriched isotopic characteristic with $^{87/86}Sr$, between 0.7107 and 0.7111, and $^{143/144}Nd$, between 0.51193 and 0.51182. The geochemical features of the Sedemte Prestola pluton imply orogenic geodynamic setting of formation as a product of more primitive magma fractionation. Isotopic characteristics and high LILE, Th and U contents support the derivation from enriched mantle source – phlogopite-bearing peridotites in the spinel stability field.

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INTRODUCTION

Late Paleozoic tectonomagmatic activity resulted in the formation of alkaline intrusions with potassic affinity, which are typical for the central and eastern parts of the Variscan orogenic edifice (Dimitrov, 1935, 1937; Kostov, 1950; Holub *et al.*, 1997; Janousek and Gerdes, 2003; Dyulgerov, 2005; Kotkova *et al.*, 2010; Krmíček *et al.*, 2016; Buzzi *et al.* 2010; Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2018). These magmatic bodies are usually several hundred meters to kilometers in width, but regardless of their small sizes, they show variable petrographic composition, in which intermediate to acid varieties predominate.

In Bulgaria, Variscan potassic alkaline rocks build up several small plutons in the Balkan Mts. area and Kraishte region. They represent hypabyss-

sal bodies intruded into Lower Paleozoic sediments. Potassic alkaline plutons do not possess direct contacts with the most voluminous calc-alkaline and high-K calc-alkaline granitoids, although they appear to be a product of one orogenic cycle (Kamenov *et al.*, 2002; Carrigan *et al.*, 2005; Peycheva *et al.*, 2006; Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2006, 2018). All alkaline plutons have a strong potassic character, with high Th, U and LILE content. Some of the plutons evolve towards peralkaline varieties, which also display HFS and REE enrichments.

GEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The Sedemte Prestola pluton ($42^{\circ}59'58''$ N; $23^{\circ}28'36''$ E) was first described by Belev (1979), who gave its petrographic description and whole

rock chemistry. Belev (1984) also provided some general outlines of the Variscan magmatic activity and brief comparison of the alkaline plutons in Bulgaria. Due to its small size and poor outcrops, the Sedemte Prestola magmatic body has stayed away from the scientific interest, and neither geochemical data nor age determination have been published. The potassic-alkaline rocks of the pluton intrude the Diabase Phyllitoid Complex (according to Belev, 1979), or Cambrian–Lower Ordovician shales (Angelov *et al.*, 2010). The contacts are sharp, steep to vertical, and the contact aureole in the country rocks is 0.30–1 m in width. The shape of the pluton is rectangular and occupies an area of ~0.15 km² (Fig. 1), with main rock type being syenite. In the studied area, there are also outcrops of granitoids of the calc-alkaline formation (the Botevgrad and Mezdreya plutons), as well as one unspecified body (probably part of the Petrohan pluton). The rocks of the Sedemte Prestola pluton are cut by fine-grained dykes of intermediate composition (diorite or basal-

tic andesite related to the Rzhana pluton); the dykes are also emplaced in the contact zone between the alkaline and country rocks. Belev (1979) described gradual changes in the facial varieties and showed them on a sketch-map. The latest observations could not confirm the previously presented data, as the dense forests and limited exposures did not allow to establish some particular features of the pluton. Regardless of these limitations, new material has recently been collected and yielded mineralogical, petrographic and geochemical data, and an attempt to date the pluton has also been made.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The data on the mineral composition were obtained by electron microprobe Cameca SX 100 WDS (Sorbonne University, Paris), working at 15 kV accelerating voltage, 10 nA; 0.6 µm beam diameter, counting time 15–20 sec. Whole-rock chemistry was analyzed by XRF Epsilon3 XLE and wet chemical analysis for FeO-Fe₂O₃ determination (at Sofia University). Trace element composition was analyzed by LA ICP-MS on Perkin Elmer ELAN DRC with New Wave UP 193FX ablation system (Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences). The beam spot was 35 µm, the beam current was 6 Hz, and the energy 7.2 mJ. NIST 610 was used as external standard, whereas the internal standard was the SiO₂ content of the minerals obtained from EMP analysis; data reduction was performed by the Sills software as recommended by Allan *et al.* (2005). Isotope tracing was performed at the Geochronology and Isotope Geochemistry Service (UCM, Spain) on an IsotopX-Phoenix (TIMS) apparatus.

PETROGRAPHY AND MINERALOGY

The rocks of the Sedemte Prestola pluton are pinkish and reddish, white and grey varieties are less common. They display massive structure and medium- to fine-grained texture. The texture is also equal-grained, the porphyritic on potassium feldspar varieties are rare; under microscope, agpaitic texture is also visible (see Fig. 2). The rocks are composed of potassium feldspar, quartz and amphibole; biotite is sporadic. Accessory phases are titanite, ilmenite, zircon and apatite. Potassium feldspar, amphibole and quartz amounts show variations that underlie the petrographic diversity of the rocks. The rock species presented are syenite, quartzsyenite and granite; as with modal increase of quartz, the rocks change from syenites to quartzsy-

Fig. 1. Sketch map of the area of Sedemte Prestola Monastery, containing potassic alkaline rocks (modified from Belev, 1979).

Fig. 2. Microphotographs of the rocks: *a*) unaltered syenite (PPL); *b*) quartzsyenite (XPL); *c*) granite (XPL); *d*) altered syenite (PPL). Abbreviations: Kfs – potassium feldspar, Q – quartz, Amph – amphibole.

enites and granites. There are no systematic changes of textures and structures with the modal variance of rock-forming minerals. The rocks are strongly weathered; imposed hydrothermal alterations are common, quartz and quartz-feldspar veins are also present. Common alteration products are chlorite, rutile and titanite; they are formed by hydrothermal destabilization of biotite, amphibole and ilmenite.

Potassium feldspar is the main mineral in the rocks; it is clear, and appears in euhedral to subhedral platy crystals with microcline grid-twinning. Its composition is homogeneous, orthoclase end-member dominates, albite (up to 8 molec. %) and celsian (up to 5 molec. %) end-members are low (Table 1). Concentrations of REE and other trace elements are below the detection limits.

Biotite is rare, often rimmed by, or completely transformed in, amphibole; in zones of hydrothermal trails, it is altered to chlorite + rutile + titanite aggregates. Biotite does not show significant vari-

ance in composition with X_{Mg} : 0.67–0.59 (Table 2). Titanium content is elevated ($TiO_2 = 2.7\text{--}4$ wt. %), whereas aluminum is low (11 wt. % Al_2O_3), reflecting the low Al_2O_3 content of the rock and the transition toward peralkaline setting. Fluorine and chlorine contents are low, attesting that water was the main fluid during the magma crystallization.

Amphibole is the main mafic mineral. It crystallizes in long prismatic crystals, surrounding feldspars and forming the agpaitic texture of the rock; it is rarely included in potassium feldspar as early liquidus phase. It shows distinct pleochroism in blue-green to brown-violet; some small crystals display pale blue color. The amphiboles belong to calcic-sodic varieties (Table 3). The presented species are richterite and ferri-winchite; ferri-katophorite and ferri-baroisite are less frequent. The main compositional variance in amphiboles is ${}^B Ca_{-1} {}^B Na_1$, magnesium character is elevated with X_{Mg} between 0.84 and 0.60, and fluorine content is up to 0.94 wt. %.

Table 1
Selected feldspar analyses, calculations on eight oxides

SiO ₂	62.29	67.66	63.36	63.63	63.79	63.81	63.94	63.05	62.59	63.26	63.91
Al ₂ O ₃	18.53	16.3	18.47	18.26	18.52	18.37	18.6	18.33	18.6	17.34	18.42
FeOt	0.3	0.31	0.89	0.77	0.52	0.42	0.83	0.64	0.57	1.17	1.28
CaO	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05
Na ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.90	0.34	0.33	0.12	0.57	0.57	0.42	0.38
K ₂ O	14.99	14.63	15.82	15.35	16.28	16.13	16.67	15.37	15.64	16.00	16.22
SrO	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
BaO	2.57	1.26	0.78	0.88	0.68	0.86	0.50	1.52	1.40	0.57	0.16
Total	99.35	100.16	99.76	99.79	100.13	99.92	100.67	99.48	99.37	98.76	100.42
Si	2.954	3.105	2.959	2.968	2.968	2.975	2.961	2.963	2.948	2.986	2.958
Al	1.036	0.881	1.017	1.004	1.016	1.010	1.015	1.015	1.033	0.965	1.005
Fe ³⁺	0.012	0.012	0.035	0.030	0.020	0.016	0.032	0.025	0.022	0.046	0.050
Ca	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002
Na	0.000	0.000	0.038	0.081	0.031	0.030	0.011	0.052	0.052	0.038	0.034
K	0.907	0.856	0.942	0.913	0.966	0.959	0.985	0.921	0.940	0.963	0.958
Sr	0.018	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ba	0.048	0.023	0.014	0.016	0.012	0.016	0.009	0.028	0.026	0.011	0.003
Total	4.975	4.877	5.006	5.013	5.013	5.006	5.013	5.004	5.020	5.009	5.010
Or	95.00	97.42	94.65	90.35	95.73	95.47	97.98	92.02	92.34	95.16	96.04
Ab	0.000	0.000	3.820	8.054	3.040	2.969	1.072	5.188	5.117	3.798	3.421
An	0.000	0.000	0.100	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.049	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.249
Cn	5.003	2.577	1.433	1.591	1.228	1.564	0.903	2.795	2.539	1.041	0.291

The [A]-site filling varies between 1 and 0.3, and this site is occupied by K and Na in equal proportions. This amphibole is relatively enriched in transition metals: V (~370 ppm) and Zn (~530 ppm). The magmatic amphiboles were reequilibrated during the late- to post-magmatic stage with development of bluish rims (probably riebeckite).

Accessory minerals are in varying proportions; among them, Fe-Ti oxides and zircon are the most common. Ilmenite is a ubiquitous phase; it is late and usually associates with amphiboles. The ilmenite is often rimmed by rutile; the microprobe analysis shows its destabilization and transition toward rutile + Fe₂O₃ (or FeOOH) assemblages. Zircon is widespread in the rocks and forms stubby bipyramids with no prismatic faces. It is red to brown, with numerous mineral inclusions. LA ICP-MS analysis showed that zircon is very rich in radiogenic elements with up to 90,000 ppm of Th and up to 17,000 ppm of U.

The precise evaluation of the intensive variables of magma crystallization (T , P , fO_2) is not possible in the absence of ilmenite-magnetite couple and the presence of sodic-calcic amphibole. From the whole-rock and mineral chemistry, we can roughly outline the conditions of crystallization of the potassic rocks. The experimental study on peralkaline acid magmas of Thompson and MacKenzie (1967)

revealed that their liquidus temperatures are in the range of 850–840 °C. The [A]-site filling in amphibole and its X_{Mg} are very sensitive to the temperature of crystallization. Intermediate richterite-ferrichterite (X_{Mg} 0.50) is stable up to 925 °C under a wide range of fO_2 conditions (Charles, 1973), the incorporation of Mg in amphiboles drastically increases the thermal stability field of the magnesio-riebeckite above 900 °C at $P = 1$ kbar on HM buffer (Ernst, 1968). The elevated magnesian character (X_{Mg}) of the studied amphiboles is in the range 84–60 (Table 3) and imply crystallization of near liquidus temperatures. The titanium in zircon thermometer (Watson *et al.*, 2006) yielded temperatures in the range of 1200–1043 °C, which are too elevated for such evolved rocks and only the lower temperature limit can be assumed as informative for the beginning of crystallization. Considering the above-mentioned, we can assume the beginning of crystallization at around or just above 900 °C, because the solidus temperature cannot be even roughly estimated in absence of appropriate geothermometers.

The presence only of microcline, the common transformation of ilmenite in rutile + hematite and the replacement of biotite by chlorite + rutile + titanite aggregates attest for abundant circulation of residual postmagmatic fluids. The diversity of hydrothermal alterations is inferred from two differ-

Table 2
Biotite composition, calculations on 22 oxides

SiO ₂	40.44	38.53	37.96	38.2
TiO ₂	2.69	3.33	3.16	4.01
Al ₂ O ₃	11.40	11.59	11.6	11.7
FeO	14.56	17.04	17.01	16.63
MnO	0.23	0.17	0.19	0.22
MgO	16.84	14	14.03	14.00
BaO	0.23	0.4	0.33	0.62
CaO	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.00
Na ₂ O	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.00
K ₂ O	9.35	9.64	8.98	9.63
F	1.40	0.77	1.02	0.97
Cl	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00
Total	97.22	95.52	94.40	95.98
O=F,Cl	0.60	0.33	0.43	0.41
Total*	96.62	95.19	93.97	95.57
Si	5.27	5.15	5.12	5.09
Ti	0.26	0.33	0.32	0.40
Al	3.50	3.65	3.69	3.67
Fe ²⁺	1.59	1.90	1.92	1.85
Mn	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02
Mg	3.27	2.79	2.82	2.78
Ba	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03
Ca	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Rb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Na	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
K	1.55	1.64	1.55	1.64
Cr	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total cat.	15.50	15.51	15.48	14.49
F	0.58	0.33	0.44	0.41
Cl	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
OH*	3.42	3.67	3.56	3.59
X _{Mg}	0.67	0.59	0.59	0.60

ent stages of these alterations: early (with transformation of potassium feldspar into microcline), and later, which is evidenced by ilmenite alteration and biotite replacement.

GEOCHEMISTRY

The rocks of the Sedemte Prestola pluton belong to the intermediate and acid varieties, as SiO₂ ranges from 62 wt. % to 75 wt. % (Table 4). With increasing silica content, MgO (4.18–0.49 wt. %) and FeO (from 4.04 wt. % to 1.46 wt. %) decrease; in the same direction, the magnesian character of the rocks and P₂O₅ also diminish (X_{Mg} 0.8–0.46). The rocks have pronounced potassium character with K₂O from 7.04 wt. % to 10.42 wt. %. The sum of alkalis (ΣK₂O + Na₂O) is in the range between 7.69 and 11.85, and combined with the low A₂O₃ (9.37–

12.97 wt. %) predetermines algaicity index indicating peralkaline whole-rock chemistry (AI between 0.9 and 1.1).

Trace elements can be subdivided into several groups according to their contents in the rocks. Transition metals are moderate, reflecting the evolved character of the rocks: Ni (77–111 ppm), Sc (5–17 ppm), V (58–143 ppm), and Co (3–17 ppm). Their contents decline towards more leucocratic varieties (Fig. 3) reflecting that, despite the small size of the pluton, fractionation of mafic minerals and apatite was an active process.

Along with LILE, Ba is most outstanding (3302–6264 ppm), whereas Rb (195–359 ppm) and Sr (93–583 ppm) show moderate contents. HFS elements display significant enrichment, which is in line with the evolution towards peralkaline varieties: Zr is between 300 ppm and 648 ppm, and Nb is between 29 ppm and 60 ppm; Th (21–99 ppm) and U (8–90 ppm) also show significant contents (Table 4).

The rocks are characterized by significant REE contents, ranging from 208 ppm to 404 ppm. This is combined with a high La_N/Lu_N ratio (32–90), which positively correlates with SiO₂ in the rocks and forms a steep trend on the chondrite-normalized diagram (Fig. 4). A negative Eu anomaly (Eu*) of 0.6–0.8 suggests that the fractionation of a specific phase, plagioclase or potassium feldspar, occurred prior to the final magma emplacement.

Isotope tracing of two samples (Table 5) shows that the rocks plot in the enriched IVth quadrant of the isotopic systematics (Fig. 5), as the initial ratios are in the interval 0.7107–0.7111 for ^{87/86}Sr_i and 0.51193–0.51182 for ^{143/144}Nd_i, respectively (309 Ma age corrected).

DATING

The SEM investigation confirmed the microscopic observations that the zircons are rich in mineral inclusions. Backscattered electron (BSE) images showed numerous bright phases evenly distributed in the zircon grains, and cathodoluminescence (CL) images revealed that these grains are structureless with no growing patterns (Fig. 6). The *in situ* LA ICP MS isotope analyses did not yield consistent results, attesting for significant radiogenic lead loss due to metamictization. *In situ* titanite U-Pb dating yields Concordia age of 308.7 ± 9.1 Ma confirming the Variscan age of the Sedemte Prestola potassic rocks (Table 6, Fig. 7). The obtained age determination places the Sedemte Prestola potassic pluton among the other Variscan potassic plutons in Bulgaria in

Table 3

Selected amphibole analyses. Calculations on 24 (O, F, C, OH) oxides in wt. %, trace elements in ppm (n.a. – not analyzed; b.d.l. – below detection limit)

SiO ₂	49.97	53.33	50.01	49.62	50.15	53.82	53.9	53.16	52.69	54.51	54.03	53.44	53.54
TiO ₂	0.23	0.44	0.32	0.54	0.41	1.45	1.35	1.26	0.85	0.77	1.21	1.29	1.43
Al ₂ O ₃	5.98	1.77	5.35	2.93	3.58	1.28	1.22	1.24	0.72	0.25	1.13	1.1	1.15
FeO	12.86	18.96	11.05	16.96	14.79	13.98	12.95	14.63	14.47	14.27	10.28	9.8	12.42
MnO	0.43	0.36	0.29	0.25	0.37	0.39	0.33	0.45	0.44	0.41	0.34	0.33	0.33
MgO	15.7	11.53	16.98	12.24	14.47	14.81	15.21	14	13.83	14.75	17.14	16.82	16.21
CaO	9.5	3.46	10.14	4.70	4.80	6.20	6.15	6.08	7.71	5.35	6.68	6.69	6.35
Na ₂ O	2.76	7.40	3.06	7.08	7.68	4.34	4.8	3.97	3.6	4.07	3.81	4.11	3.73
K ₂ O	0.56	1.26	0.48	1.24	0.84	1.97	2.02	1.64	1.49	2.81	2.40	2.46	2.08
F	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	0.5	0.50	0.63	0.52	0.77	0.94	0.53	0.59
Cl	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01
Total	97.99	98.51	97.68	95.56	97.09	98.53	98.27	96.80	96.11	97.64	97.58	96.35	97.59
Si	7.083	7.782	7.117	7.490	7.331	7.730	7.774	7.761	7.849	7.905	7.744	7.784	7.666
Al	0.917	0.218	0.883	0.510	0.617	0.217	0.207	0.213	0.126	0.043	0.191	0.189	0.194
Ti	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.052	0.053	0.018	0.026	0.024	0.053	0.065	0.027	0.140
T	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000
Al	0.083	0.086	0.014	0.012	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ti	0.025	0.048	0.034	0.061	0.000	0.103	0.128	0.112	0.071	0.031	0.065	0.114	0.014
Fe ³⁺	1.039	0.625	0.776	0.543	0.793	0.532	0.336	0.658	0.200	0.653	0.511	0.254	0.803
Fe ²⁺	0.485	1.688	0.539	1.598	1.015	1.147	1.226	1.129	1.603	1.077	0.721	0.940	0.685
Mn	0.052	0.044	0.035	0.032	0.046	0.047	0.040	0.056	0.056	0.050	0.041	0.041	0.040
Mg	3.317	2.507	3.601	2.754	3.153	3.170	3.269	3.046	3.071	3.188	3.661	3.651	3.459
C	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.007	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000
Mg	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ca	1.443	0.541	1.546	0.760	0.752	0.954	0.950	0.951	1.231	0.831	1.026	1.044	0.974
Na	0.557	1.459	0.454	1.240	1.248	1.046	1.050	1.049	0.769	1.144	0.974	0.956	1.026
B	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	1.976	2.000	2.000	2.000
K	0.101	0.235	0.087	0.239	0.157	0.361	0.372	0.305	0.283	0.520	0.439	0.457	0.380
Na	0.202	0.635	0.391	0.833	0.929	0.163	0.293	0.075	0.271	0.000	0.085	0.205	0.010
A	0.303	0.869	0.478	1.071	1.085	0.524	0.665	0.380	0.554	0.520	0.524	0.662	0.390
F	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	0.227	0.228	0.291	0.245	0.353	0.426	0.244	0.267
Cl	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	0.002	0.024	0.002	0.005	0.000	0.005	0.000	0.002
OH*	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	1.770	1.747	1.707	1.750	1.647	1.569	1.756	1.730
X _{Mg}	0.87	0.60	0.87	0.63	0.76	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.66	0.75	0.84	0.80	0.83
Li	10.1	21.2		La	6.6	11.6							
Sc	39.5	43.6		Ce	11.1	17.9							
V	367.3	372.9		Pr	1.0	1.0							
Cr	682.4	851.0		Nd	6.0	5.4							
Co	41.7	56.2		Sm	b.d.l.	b.d.l.							
Zn	522.7	547.2		Eu	b.d.l.	b.d.l.							
Rb	10.1	13.1		Gd	1.7	b.d.l.							
Sr	826.4	872.6		Tb	b.d.l.	b.d.l.							
Y	3.6	6.5		Dy	1.0	b.d.l.							
Zr	90.6	169.6		Ho	b.d.l.	0.3							
Nb	11.1	22.6		Er	b.d.l.	b.d.l.							
Ba	18.4	34.0		Yb	2.4	2.5							
Hf	4.6	8.4		Lu	0.6	0.4							
Pb	24.0	25.6											

the narrow time frame of magma generation (Carrigan *et al.*, 2005; Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2006; Peytcheva *et al.*, 2006; Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2018). This age also limits the time of introduction of the intermediate fine-grained dykes from the Rzhana pluton (microdiorite/basaltic andesites), which cut the granitoid rocks.

DISCUSSION

The Sedemte Prestola pluton has several distinctive features that should be noted. The contents of SiO₂, MgO, FeO, Ni, V, Sc, the negative Eu anomaly and linear trends on the Harker diagrams indicate an origin via differentiation from more mafic magma. On the Y-Nb-Ce diagram (Fig. 8), the rocks plot in the A₁ field, which is typical for A-type granitoids that are a product of basic magma fractionation (deriving from an OIB-like mantle source). The degree of potassium enrichment and relatively elevated Ni, Co, Sc and V contents, coupled with X_{Mg} of the rocks, exclude their derivation from crystal source, since these contents exceed those established in all crustal reservoirs (*e.g.*, Taylor and McLennan, 1988; Rudnick and Gao, 2003). Moreover, melting of mafic rocks in crustal setting cannot produce such a highly potassium magma with peralkaline affinity, as the most alkali-rich magmas produced by experiments are quartzmonzodioritic to quartzmonzonitic (Sisson *et al.*, 2005). All these geochemical particularities are supportive of derivation from a mantle source, from which the extracting magmas have undergone *en route* differentiation. Due to the slightly evolved character of the rocks, it is not possible to define strictly the depth of the magma source (*e.g.*, in spinel or garnet stability fields) as the degree of REE fractionation (La_N/Lu_N) might have been modified during the differentiation. However, in all analyzed samples, the trend of MREE and HREE is very flat and it seems that they have not been affected by fractionation (Tb_N/Lu_N ~2 for all rocks). This flat trend, coupled with Lu_{rock}/Lu_{chondrite} of 10 for the least-differentiated samples, is indicative of a spinel-bearing mantle source.

The extent of the incompatible element enrichment for the rocks from the Sedemte Prestola pluton shows a marked difference: hygromagmatophiles (Rb, Ba, Th, U) transported by fluids are enriched between 4 and 20 times compared to the average crust (*sensu* Rudnick and Gao, 2003), whereas the extent of LREE and HFSE enrichment is 2–8 (Table 4). These features are evidenced by the distribution

Table 4
Whole-rock composition

Sample	G-2	G-3	G 8+	2 G	5 G
SiO ₂	68.22	61.88	62.39	75.83	66.79
TiO ₂	0.50	0.92	0.9	0.55	0.63
Al ₂ O ₃	12.97	10.73	11.91	9.37	12.34
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.10	3.30	3.80	2.14	1.48
FeO	1.46	4.04	1.9	1.6	1.74
MnO	0.10	0.17	0.07	0.04	0.06
MgO	0.49	4.07	4.18	0.77	2.46
CaO	0.42	2.96	2.95	0.62	1.31
Na ₂ O	0.90	1.10	1.19	0.65	1.43
K ₂ O	10.38	7.68	9.05	7.04	10.42
P ₂ O ₅	0.06	0.29	0.52	0.13	0.38
H ₂ O-	n.a.	n.a.	0.03	0.29	0.24
L.O.I.	0.24	2.38	0.79	0.66	0.59
Total	98.37	99.74	99.68	99.69	99.87
A.I.	0.98	0.94	0.99	0.93	1.10
X _{Mg}	0.47	0.66	0.80	0.46	0.72
Sc	12	13	17	5	11
Co	3	15	14	10	17
Ni	15	61	77	19	11
V	98	143	119	58	77
Cu	16	60	n.a.	55	26
Zn	73	77	172	39	45
Ga	22	21	19	79	112
Rb	334	195	232	271	359
Sr	264	383	583	93	226
Cs	4	3	2	3	6
Ba	6264	3302	4595	3586	5476
Y	9	20	22	7	7
Zr	301	572	648	438	360
Hf	10	18	17	13	13
Nb	60	54	54	29	32
Mo	4.8	3.1	n.a.	7.6	2.2
Ta	2.5	3.4	5.2	1.1	2.8
Pb	5	6	156	136	289
Th	99	21	99	69	33
U	46	90	19	15	8
W	8	20	n.a.	9	3
La	120.6	79.1	68	106.5	51.6
Ce	188.7	150.0	136.7	163.5	98.6
Pr	17.9	15.3	15.5	12.7	9.3
Nd	59.1	55.7	60.4	36.9	33.8
Sm	8.1	10.2	10.9	4.4	6.5
Eu	1.22	1.57	2.09	0.83	0.91
Gd	4.08	5.86	7.25	2.17	3.50
Tb	0.43	0.81	0.84	0.29	0.35
Dy	1.94	3.79	4.44	0.91	1.46
Ho	0.34	0.70	0.76	0.28	0.20
Er	0.81	1.83	1.68	0.62	0.62
Tm	0.12	0.25	0.25	0.12	0.08
Yb	0.78	1.77	1.34	1.15	0.64
Lu	0.14	0.27	0.22	0.17	0.13
ΣREE	404	327	311	331	208
Eu*	0.65	0.62	0.72	0.82	0.58

A.I. – aipacity index: molar (Na₂O+K₂O)/Al₂O₃

Fig. 3. Harker diagrams for the rocks of the Sedemte Prestola pluton.

on the spider diagram (Fig. 9), on which large-ion lithophiles (LIL), Th and U represent significant enrichment exceeding that of the other incompatible elements (Nb, Ta, Zr, LREE). The rocks also show Nb-Ta, P and Ti negative anomalies as this geochemical characteristic is typical for rocks from orogenic settings. On the Ta/Yb–Th/Yb diagram (Fig. 10), the studied potassic rocks show devia-

tion from a mantle array towards significant subduction-related input. From it, it can be inferred that contamination with upper or middle crustal materials cannot produce the observed geochemical characteristics as the enrichment levels of the incompatible hygromagmatophile element (Th) far exceed those of the incompatible conservative element (Ta). The isotopic characteristics of rocks can

Fig. 4. REE distribution for the studied rocks. Normalization on chondrite C1 (Sun and McDonough, 1989).

Fig. 5. Sr–Nd plot for the studied syenite compared to other potassic rocks: Bohemian rocks (Holub and Janoušek, 2003); Spanish lamproites (Nelson *et al.*, 1986); Leucite hills (Vollmer *et al.*, 1984); ultrapotassic rocks from Tibet (Miller *et al.*, 1999); Shipka potassic syenites (Dyulgerov, 2011); GLOSS-average (Plank and Langmuir, 1998); EMI and EMII (Zindler and Hart, 1986).

Fig. 6. Backscattered electron (BSE) and cathodoluminescence images of zircons from the Sedemte Prestola pluton.

also be explained in terms of involvement of crustal components via subduction: materials with high Rb/Sr and low Sm/Nd ratios can be assigned to the introduced crustal materials into the mantle source. Rubidium and neodymium are more incompatible and mobile elements from the couples, thus they would be easily added to the mantle through metasomatizing fluids or magmas from the descending slab. Thus, over time, a source with high $^{87/86}\text{Sr}_i$ and low $^{143/144}\text{Nd}_i$ signature would be generated.

The Metasomatized Mantle represented by MARID xenoliths (Dawson and Smith, 1977; Dawson, 1987) is considered as a source for generation

of strongly alkaline magmas (Foley, 1992). Phlogopite and potassic-richterites are common minerals in MARID type xenoliths and their decomposition is considered as the main source of Na and K for the magmas. Experiments showed that both phlogopite and potassic-richterite are stable under variable conditions, from 0.5 GPa to 10 GPa (Yodder and Kushiro, 1969; Konzett 1997; Tiepolo *et al.*, 2003, and references therein). Compositions of liquids derived from melting of phlogopite and potassic-richterite-bearing assemblage (Konzett, 1997), and only of potassic-richterite-bearing assemblage (Tiepolo *et al.*, 2003) are very potassium-rich and peralkaline.

Table 5
Sr and Nd isotopic data for the rocks; $\lambda^{87\text{Rb}} = 1.42\text{E-}11$; $\lambda^{142\text{Sm}} = 6.54\text{E-}12$

Sample	G 8+	5G
Rb (ppm)	232	359
Sr (ppm)	583	226
Age (Ma)	309	309
$^{87}\text{Rb}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	1.15225	4.60656
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	0.715714	0.731370
$\pm 2\sigma$	3	3
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ (i)	0.710647	0.711113
Sm (ppm)	10.92	6.52
Nd (ppm)	60.35	33.79
$^{147}\text{Sm}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.10894119	0.11617326
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.51215341	0.51205693
$\pm 2\sigma$	1	2
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$ (i)	0.5119330	0.5118219
CHURt	0.5122401	0.5122401
ϵNd	-6.0	-8.2

However, the $\text{K}_2\text{O}/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ molecular ratios of these liquids are between 2 and 3.5, so they are lower than the same ratio for the rocks of the Sedemte Prestola pluton (4.6–7). The very high potassium content and the K/Na ratio of the studied rocks are in favor of phlogopite-bearing mantle source. Experiments on relatively low pressures between 1 GPa and 3 GPa (Yodder and Kushiro, 1969) show that the decomposition of phlogopite is just above 1300 °C. This temperature can be accepted as liquidus temperature of mantle peridotite and is in reasonable agreement with subcontinental geotherm.

The isotopic characteristics of the Sedemte Prestola pluton are similar to other Variscan potassic rocks both from Bulgaria and Bohemia (Czech Republic): the potassic melasyenites (durbachites) and minettes (Janoušek *et al.*, 1995; Holub and Janoušek, 2003), Shipka potassic melasyenites

Fig. 7. Concordia plot of titanite U-Pb data with applied corrections (Andersen, 2002) from the Sedemte Prestola pluton with best fit regression line. Analyses are shown as 2σ error ellipses.

Fig. 8. Studied rocks plotted on Y–Nb–Ce diagram (Eby, 1992).

Table 6
Isotope ratios and ages of G8 titanite dating with applied Andersen (2002) correction (c - center, r - rim)

Crystals	Isotopic ratios							Ages					
	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{235}\text{U}$	2σ	$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$	2σ	Rho	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$	2σ	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{235}\text{U}$	2σ	$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$	2σ	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$	2σ
1 r	0.364	0.014	0.049	0.002	0.124	0.053	0.000	312	10	308	10	341	12
1 c	0.740	0.100	0.061	0.008	0.173	0.113	0.013	549	52	375	48	1600	220
1 r	0.384	0.022	0.052	0.003	0.127	0.054	0.000	331	16	327	18	361	17
2 r	0.369	0.020	0.049	0.003	0.130	0.053	0.000	315	15	311	16	341	16
2 r	0.386	0.026	0.051	0.003	0.124	0.054	0.000	333	19	325	19	359	20
4 c	0.368	0.020	0.050	0.003	0.125	0.053	0.000	315	15	312	15	338	15
4 r	0.369	0.030	0.047	0.004	0.174	0.057	0.002	318	21	296	24	421	56
5 r	0.682	0.071	0.059	0.005	0.170	0.102	0.009	512	41	370	32	1380	170
5 c	0.741	0.056	0.063	0.003	0.186	0.100	0.009	552	32	392	20	1340	160

Fig. 9. Spidergram for the studied rock. Normalization on Primitive Mantle (Sun and McDonough, 1989).

(Dyulgerov, 2011) and Svidnya and Buhovo-Seslavtsi intrusions (Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2007). The Sedemte Prestola rocks show close mineralogical and geochemical resemblance with the peralkaline dykes from the Lutskan pluton and the syeniteporphyries (bostonite) from the Buhovo-Seslavtsi pluton (Dimitrov, 1935; Dyulgerov *et al.*, 2006). All these rocks are slightly peralkaline, quartz- and sodic-calcic amphibole-bearing. The degree of incompatible element enrichment is prominent and common accessories are titanite, rutile and apatite. The whole-rock chemistry and isotope composition of the Sedemte Prestola granitoids share similarities with other Variscan alkaline rocks: the ultrapotassic syenites from the Moldanubian Zone (Holub, 1997) and ultrapotassic dykes from the Moldanubian and Saxo-Thuringian zones (Krmíček *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

The Sedemte Prestola pluton is a small magmatic body of Variscan age intruded at shallow depth. Its geochemical features suggest that it is a differentiated portion part of more primitive magma and outcrops as an apical part of a deeply situated more mafic body. Its geochemical signature is rather inherited from the source than acquired through assimilation of crustal materials *en route* to the surface. The strong alkaline character, trace element enrichment and radiogenic isotopic signature of the rocks are in favor of derivation from a metasomatized mantle source, enriched through introduction of crustal material during previous tectonic events. The high K/Na and $\text{Lu}_{\text{rock}}/\text{Lu}_{\text{chondrite}}$ ratios attest to

Fig. 10. Studied rocks plotted on Ta/Yb vs Th/Yb diagram (Pearce, 1983). MCC – middle continental crust; UCC – upper continental crust (both taken from Rudnick and Gao, 2003); Vectors: S – sediment input, CC – crustal contamination, WPE – within plate enrichment, FC – fractional crystallization.

generation from a phlogopite-bearing source in the spinel stability field.

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